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Photonic cognition of liquid crystal polymers for unlocking electrical locomotion

In our work, we introduce light-triggered cognition within our electrically functionalized spiropyran-doped liquid crystal network (SP-LCN) smart materials. Thus, we were able to train SP-LCNs to respond to reduced electrical fields. The trained behavior was eventually forgotten by the material, mimicking human learning. We envision that our intelligent materials will advance the domain of learning material to enable self-optimizing devices, such as prosthetics that can actively acclimatize to their user over time.

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Highlights

Material properties of SP-LCNs are tunable with UV training stimuli

The response of SP-LCNs can be trained to actuate with reduced electrical stimuli

Trained SP-LCNs eventually forget their training history

Demonstrate

Proof-of-concept of performance with intended application/response

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Article

Photonic cognition of liquid crystal polymers for unlocking electrical locomotion

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SUMMARY

The artificial replication of learning phenomena is an emerging domain with proven social impact. In this paper, we advance composite responsive material behavior toward learning by inducing memory-dependent functions through repeated exposure to a priming stimulus. For this, we integrate a photochromic spiropyran dopant into our liquid crystal network (LCN) to control its electrical actuation. UV light irradiation increases charge density by triggering the spiropyran-to-merocyanine zwitterion conversion, “gating” the permittivity of the LCN, and reducing the alternating electric field strength threshold required for actuation by up to 67.8% from its initial state. This UV-gating effect persists in the LCN as a memorized behavior. Resembling biological memory, the UV-gated memory is reversible and erased from the material over time. This is accelerated by up to 20% by irradiation with a green light “memory-wiping” agent. We envision that our work will contribute to the development of artificially intelligent materials for self-learning appliances and medical devices.

INTRODUCTION

The replication of learning phenomena within artificial systems has set the precedent that the ability to learn is not limited to living organisms.¹ These advances have inspired the advent of computational artificial intelligence and robotic mechanical neural networks.^{2,3} This concept currently manifests within the materials domain as stimuli-responsive smart materials, which can be subjected to selected stimuli to trigger various engineered changes in their material properties.^{4–8} Liquid crystals (LCs) are smart materials that are in the limelight for their anisotropic properties and their programmable responsiveness, actuation, and compliance.^{8–16} Yet, in order to advance LC actuation behavior toward the level of artificial intelligence, the capabilities of biological organisms must be mimicked by integrating the element of learning. Development of material learning, expressed through electronic or chemical responses, is pursued by research groups with various foci, ranging from medicine to electrics and robotics.^{17,18} Liquid crystal networks (LCNs) offer the opportunity to extend material learning to reversible actuation responses of soft matter, allowing for tangible communication or interaction with people or the wider world more like a living organism.^{19–25} Pioneering work on LCN learning materials has shown that this material is capable of abiding to the principles of basic classical conditioning^{26,27}; LCN actuation can be defined as an unconditioned response paired to an unconditioned stimulus, such as heat, that can be paired to conditioned stimulus, such as light, in which both activate the actuation behavior of LCN with conditioning. Yet, to unlock more learning potential within LCNs, its memory properties must be further explored and developed. This includes memory-erasure behavior, as this complements learning by streamlining cognition and is hence equally

PROGRESS AND POTENTIAL

The advent of artificial intelligence in computing is a major development of the 21st century that has established the precedent that learning can be replicated synthetically. Smart materials, capable of reacting to specific stimuli to perform actions, are prime contenders for bringing learning principles to the materials domain. In our work, we demonstrate material cognition by training spiropyran-doped liquid crystal network composites with UV light to alter their material properties and subsequently increase their responsiveness to electrical stimuli. Thus, training allows the material to actuate with electrical stimuli that would otherwise have been insufficient. Mimicking human learning phenomena, our material is able to “forget” its training over time and revert to its original behavior. We envision that our intelligent materials will advance the domain of learning materials toward self-optimizing devices, such as prosthetics that acclimatize to their user over time.

significant biologically, yet it is often not in the spotlight in smart material innovation.²⁸ Therefore, akin to a human being forgetting a memory, our LCNs must also be able to revert to their initial behavior over time.²⁹

In our work, we introduce memory into our LCN materials through responsiveness to a UV priming stimulus. We define the memory induced into our LCNs as implicit, as this does not involve a computational unit or subject awareness. Our UV stimulus is defined as a primer, as it commits the LCN to an event it experiences frequently and recently, which in turn impels our LCN to alter its behavior for following events.²⁶ This process is configured by incorporating the active dopant spiropyran (SP) into our LCNs. SP-doped LCNs are initially not responsive to electric fields since they do not have significant polarity. Yet, UV exposure can cleave the carbon–oxygen bond in SPs to convert them to merocyanine (MC) zwitterions. MC zwitterions possess a positively charged nitrogen moiety and a negatively charged oxygen moiety of identical magnitudes but opposite polarities.³⁰ This induced polarity activates, or “gates,” the electrical responsiveness of the SP-doped LCN. Furthermore, we developed two methods to train our SP-doped LCN to be electrically responsive, namely continuous and pulsed UV priming modes. The continuous mode involves the sustained exposure of the UV priming stimuli, which results in less driving force required for the SP-doped LCN to show responsive behavior. On the other hand, the pulsed mode constitutes periodic exposure to the UV priming stimulus, which introduces an additional low-frequency oscillation to induce further compliance of our SP-doped LCNs to priming. Besides our priming modes, we endow our materials with memory-erasure functions that originate from the MC-to-SP back relaxation. Therefore, without sustained priming, the acquired electrical responsiveness is lost over time. The memorized behavior can be further extinguished by the application of green light as a memory-wiping agent. This combined memory-erasure and memory-forming behavior has potential as a foundation for more complete material learning phenomena, enabling mimicry of natural functions within human brains. Our SP-doped LCN memory materials reflect their potential in creating intelligent effects that can prospectively be utilized within medical, aerospace, and smart haptic applications.^{31,32}

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Priming phenomenon in SP-doped LCN materials

Our memory materials consist of cross-linked LC diacrylates and monoacrylates, namely RM82 and RM105, respectively, doped with an SP variant. SPs are a class of photochromic organic compounds that consist of two hetero-cyclical carbon groups bound by a single carbon atom. The carbon–oxygen bond in the SP molecule can be cleaved by UV exposure, converting the SP to MC. MC is a zwitterion with a positively charged nitrogen moiety and a negatively charged oxygen moiety of identical magnitudes but opposite polarities.³⁰ The reversible photochromic SP-to-MC conversion enables switching between the lower- and higher-polarity states. Our reactive mesogen mixture was optimized for its wide monomeric processing window and ideal mechanical properties in its polymeric state. Both of these molecules have relatively low dipole moments to ensure good contrast between the SP and MC states. The selected SP dopant possesses nitro-functional groups that engage in hydrogen bonding and are stabilized in the internal LCN environment, which facilitates the SP-to-MC conversion.³³ SP dopant is added to the LC mixture before curing and is arrested in the network during polymerization. The final polymerized film was electrically functionalized as a capacitor by sputter-coating 10-nm-thick layers of gold on the top and bottom surfaces, as illustrated in Figure 1A. The integrity of the sputtered gold layers on the SP-doped LCN decreases after initial

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Figure 1. SP-doped LCN (SP-LCN) capacitor construction and principles of the UV-gating effect

(A) Annotated footage and 3D illustration of the SP-LCN applied as a dielectric within a capacitor and schematics of the constituents of the material: (1) RM82, (2) RM105, and (3) SP.

(B) Schematic of implicit memory behavior in SP-LCNs: (i) initial state, (ii) response to electric actuation stimuli with no loaded memory, (iii) implicit memory loading through the UV-gated SP-to-MC transition within the LCN material, (iv) memorized increase to responsiveness to electric actuation stimuli, (v) memory erasure to restore standard response to electric actuation stimuli via heating or green light illumination to promote the MC-to-SP transition, and (vi) UV illumination to reload forgotten implicit memory to reinstate increased responsiveness to electric actuation stimuli.

(C) Annotated Nyquist plot displaying the changes in imaginary and real components of impedance upon application of the UV-gating effect on a capacitor utilizing SP-LCN as the dielectric material. UV gating was induced through UV irradiation of the sample with an intensity of 110 Wm^{-2} for an extended session of 5 min; annotations show the circuit used to model the SP-LCN capacitor during analysis.

(D) Graphical representation of the UV-gating effect on the impedance of an SP-LCN capacitor after UV illumination of the sample with 110 Wm^{-2} intensity for an extended session of 5 min. An annotated window focuses on the frequency ranges where the UV-gating effect is the greatest, marked in gray broken lines on the central graph.

(E) Graphical representation of the UV-gating effect on the capacitance of an SP-LCN capacitor after UV illumination of the sample with 110 Wm^{-2} intensity for an extended session of 5 min. Annotations show the schematic of the formation of MC zwitterions, corresponding to the peaks on the capacitance plot, that would be taking place within the LCN matrix to induce the UV-gating effect.

deformations yet does not degrade further after a certain state, as shown in Figure S1; experiments are conducted with the gold layer in the “broken-in” state, as the electrical behavior of this configuration is constant. For an ideal response for gauging the reaction of the SP-doped LCN to a stimuli, splay alignment is set within the LCN. This state involves LC molecular configuration progressing in a gradient from planar to homeotropic over the thickness of the film, as can be inferred from the polarized optical microscopy images in Figure S2. As a result, upon loss of molecular order, a unidirectional bending is induced.

The selected behavior for memorization in our SP-doped LCN material is the ability to gain reversible responsiveness, expressed as actuation, to an electric field through repeated exposure to a separate UV priming stimulus, as shown in Figure 1B. Upon exposing our SP-doped LCNs to the UV priming stimulus, the SP-to-MC conversion is initiated, inducing an increase in charge density and gating the polarizability of our material; we refer to this

phenomenon as UV gating. UV gating of our splay-aligned SP-doped LCN samples is always performed by exposing them to UV light from their planarly aligned surface. As a dielectric within a capacitor, UV gating of our SP-doped LCN material causes an impedance drop while capacitance increases, as can be inferred from its decreased curve radius in the Nyquist plot in [Figure 1C](#). In a typical sample, the SP dopant concentration is 5 wt %. With UV light irradiation, at an intensity of approximately 110 Wm^{-2} for an extended session of 5 min, the SP-to-MC conversion is driven to saturation. This decreases the impedance of the SP-doped LCN capacitor by 32.2%, or by 254.73Ω for a typical sample, at 474 kHz, as can be gauged from [Figure 1D](#). The UV-gating effect was observed to be greatest at operating frequencies lower than 500 kHz, beyond which the effect recedes until it becomes negligible at alternating current (AC) frequencies over 6 MHz. This phenomenon can be compared to the behavior of an analog capacitor when its capacitance is bypassed at higher-frequency AC, as is shown in [Figure 1E](#) where UV gating enhances the capacitive properties of our SP-doped LCN system.³⁴

UV gating leads to greater charging of the SP-doped LCN capacitor as well as greater polarization within the LCN itself. This effect can be translated from the molecular to the macroscopic level through the application of an AC electric field, which can oscillate polarizable components within the our LCNs to generate free volume in the network.^{35–38} With adequate AC electric field strength to induce sufficient incoupling, our material can be actuated. The LCN deformation for both UV-gated and non-UV-gated samples is proportional to the strength and frequency of the electric field, as shown in [Figures 2A](#) and [2B](#).³⁹ The bending response of our LCN film is quantified through image analysis, which is based on the position of the free end of the SP-doped LCN film as depicted in the annotations in [Figure 2C](#). Below certain electric field strength and AC frequency thresholds, we do not observe measurable deformation. With UV gating, the actuation is primed in our material as recorded in [Video S1](#) and justified by the decrease in the electrical thresholds for UV-gated actuation as shown in [Figure 2A](#). This figure also indicates that the threshold voltage is frequency dependent, where increasing the AC frequency reduces the threshold voltage, and vice versa. We postulate that this trend stems from a temperature rise induced by the high-frequency electric field. This would also influence the actuation of the LCN, as this material is inherently temperature responsive. The impact of the thermal effect was investigated by observing the differences in actuation for the thermally heated and electrically actuated samples presented in [Figures 2D](#), [S3](#), and [S4](#). We remarked that the SP-doped LCN material was able to deform up to 50% more when electrically driven than through purely thermal effects, as compared in [Figure S5](#). Essentially, infrared (IR) video measurements in [Video S2](#), where the maximum film temperature does not exceed 40°C , show that the observed LCN actuation is greater than expected for the current film temperature. We attribute this difference to the additional action of dielectric actuation stimuli in combination with pure thermal stimuli from Joule heating or dielectric heating when the SP-doped LCNs are actuated electrically. Moreover, UV gating was not observed to increase the temperature of the SP-doped LCN system significantly despite increasing material actuation, as shown by a maximum temperature fluctuation of 2.5°C from the average in [Figures 2E](#) and [S6](#) and [Video S3](#). Thus, the thermal effect of UV light absorption is determined not to be a factor for the improved actuation responsiveness of UV-gated samples, which is reflected by the non-response of our material recorded in [Video S4](#) and justified by the temperature measurements in [Figure S7](#). Instead, the greater responsiveness from UV gating originates from the increase in the capacitance and the inherently linked dielectric constant of the SP-doped LCN component leading to an increase in the dielectric actuation of the material. Therefore, we confirm that the UV-gating phenomenon does not induce actuation independently; instead, it trains a property into the material that was not present prior, which is memorized to facilitate actuation.

Figure 2. Actuation principles and the effects of UV gating

(A) Graphical representation of the threshold reduction for the electric field strength required for SP-LCN actuation within a capacitor through the UV-gating effect by UV illumination of the sample with 110 Wm^{-2} intensity for an extended session of 5 min.

(B) Graphical representation of the actuation threshold for electrical actuation and the proportionality of deformation and electric field strength beyond the actuation threshold; the UV-gated sample was illuminated by UV light of 110 Wm^{-2} intensity for a session of 3 min.

(C) Footage of the actuation effect induced by UV gating with electrical and UV parameters: (i) no electric field, no UV illumination; (ii) $75 \text{ V}/\mu\text{m}$ at 500 kHz, no UV illumination; (iii) $75 \text{ V}/\mu\text{m}$ at 500 kHz, 110 Wm^{-2} ; and (iv) no electric field, no UV illumination. The image analysis method used to gauge the deformation angle (θ) is annotated on the footage where deformation takes place in (ii), (iii), and (iv).

(D) Graphical representation of the mismatch of actuation deformation between thermal and electric stimuli ranging from 0 to $100 \text{ V}/\mu\text{m}$ at 500 kHz.

(E) Annotated IR footage of SP-LCN material deformation upon UV gating. The sample was illuminated by UV light of 110 Wm^{-2} intensity for an extended session of 3 min.

Continuous and pulsed UV-gated actuation of the SP-doped LCN capacitor

We developed two modes of UV gating for our LCN memory materials, namely continuous and pulsed UV illumination. Continuous UV gating involves sustained exposure to UV light before electrical field is applied, while pulsed UV gating involves repeated shorter periods of UV illumination followed by electrical field application.

Continuous UV gating induces a near-linear increase in the actuation of the material over time, as depicted in Figure 3A, that is in phase with the SP-to-MC conversion kinetics observed through UV-visible (UV-vis) spectrophotometry in Figure S8. The maximum memorized material behavior is expected when the SP-to-MC conversion is saturated, and Figure 3B shows that the saturation point increases with increasing UV irradiation intensity, which suggests that UV illumination intensity can be used to control the extent of UV gating. Despite UV-intensity dependence, we believe that there is little to no MC gradient in our samples due to the nature of the SP-to-MC transition, which induces an absorption band shift from around 350 to 580 nm, as shown in Figure S9. This causes the MC to become transparent to the initial activating UV stimulus and allows it to incident the remaining SP with minimal hindrance, as further investigated in Figure S10. Additionally, the absorbance band of our LC is around 300 nm, which means that the thickness of the sample also would

Figure 3. Analysis of UV-gated actuation and the effect of the pulsed UV-gating effect

All electrically actuated samples were driven with 75 V/ μm AC at 500 kHz.

(A) Graphical representation of the actuation of an SP-LCN capacitor upon UV gating.

(B) Graphical representation of SP-to-MC conversion with various intensities of UV illumination.

(C) Graphical representation of the deformation enhancement within the SP-LCNs with varying SP concentrations; samples were UV gated with UV light of 110 Wm^{-2} intensity for 3 min.

(D and E) Graphical comparison of the UV-gating cycling-induced deformation increases (D) in SP-LCN samples with varying cycle length periods (E) and their corresponding expected SP-to-MC conversion; the applied UV intensity was 55 Wm^{-2} .

(F) Graphical comparison of the effectiveness of UV-gated actuation with network former inclusion within the SP-LCN material. The intensity of UV illumination was 55 Wm^{-2} .

not have a significant effect on the strength of the UV stimulus throughout the sample, as shown in Figure S11, where actuation decreases with increasing thickness in a manner that is expected mechanically of a thicker sample. Yet, the saturation point can also be controlled through the concentration of SP dopant within our material. As shown in Figure 3C, the greater the concentration of the SP dopant, the greater the memory limit and memorization rate of our material become.

On the other hand, pulsed UV gating induces a smaller photostationary deformation that increases with every applied cycle until it reaches a maximum. The potential difference applied across the SP-doped LCN was cycled together with UV illumination, where the magnitude of applied voltage was retained during UV illumination and removed upon the absence of UV light. Shorter pulses lead to greater memory efficiency and magnitude, as shown in the comparison in Figure 3D. Surprisingly, despite the lower SP-to-MC conversion in pulsed modes, as shown in Figure 3E, the deformation angle achieved is 226.86% greater for pulsing UV gating at 2 Hz than at 0.25 Hz. In contrast to the constant, high-frequency oscillating stimulus applied by the AC electric field with continuous UV gating, pulsed UV gating introduces a lower-frequency oscillation to further increase the system's mechanical compliance to actuation.⁴⁰ As observed in Figures 3D and 3E, greater UV pulsing frequency allows for an enhanced UV-gating effect. To further investigate the effect of

Figure 4. Analysis of network and relaxation phenomena

(A) Graphical comparison of the strength of the relaxation phenomenon in ambient conditions with network former inclusion within the SP-LCN material.

(B) Graphical comparison of MC-to-SP relaxation within environments of various 565-nm-wavelength light intensities.

(C) Graphical representation of the relaxation enhancement within the SP-LCN capacitor with the presence of 110 Wm⁻² green light against ambient conditions.

(D) Comparison of the forgetting effect with the presence of electric fields of different strengths at 500 kHz and an environment with no electric field applied.

material plasticity on the UV-gating effect, we tuned the network properties of our material by altering the composition of our LCNs by its ratio of network-forming RM82 LC content. We observed an enhanced response to pulsed UV gating with reduced cross-linking, as shown in Figures 3F and S12, which shows that altering LCN composition is an additional factor for tuning the extent of UV-gated actuation. This suggests that a reduced elastic modulus allows MC zwitterions to incouple greater energy from the applied AC electric field and subsequently oscillate with greater amplitude to further disturb the network.³⁹

Memory-erasure phenomenon

Akin to human memory, we endow our LCN films with the ability to “forget” if repetitive priming is ceased. This occurs as the MC-to-SP conversion becomes dominant without the UV priming stimulus. This relaxation phenomenon removes the effect of material memory over time until the actuation behavior returns to its initial state. The relaxation kinetics is dependent on network plasticity and environmental conditions, such as temperature and light, as shown in the different rates of deformation recovery and MC-to-SP conversion in Figures 4A, S13, and 4B, respectively. In the dark, saturation of the MC-to-SP conversion occurs in 167 min, as shown in Figure S14; the deformation enhancement from material memory persists in proportion to the MC presence in the SP-doped LCN throughout relaxation. Relaxation can be accelerated by exposing MC to its maximum absorption wavelength in the band of green light. As shown in Figure 4B, the MC-to-SP relaxation

occurs in approximately 400 s with 565 nm green light of an intensity of 110 Wm^{-2} . The forgetting effect of this SP-to-MC relaxation was tested in [Figure 4C](#), which indicates that green light can be applied as a memory-erasing agent. However, heat generation of the electric field would further promote the SP-to-MC conversion and stimulate forgetting until the initial state, as shown in [Figure 4D](#). Thermal effects within our SP-doped LCN system were shown to accelerate relaxation similarly to green light with illumination intensities of 110 Wm^{-2} and sample temperatures over 80°C ; relaxation effects of green light were further demonstrated by limiting the final UV-gated actuation of SP-doped LCN samples, as shown in [Figure S15](#). After complete memory erasure, the response of the material to an alternating electric field is fully recovered without hysteresis. The memory-erasure phenomenon highlights the reversible nature of the SP-to-MC conversion and implies that the UV-gating effect can be applied for more complex material training.

Demonstrating SP-doped LCN material memory in a switchable array

Based on the memory properties of our LCN materials, we produced a switchable array that can be primed to produce certain recognizable forms, such as letters or other symbols, through the miniaturized UV-gating technique illustrated in [Figure 5A](#). As illustrated in [Figure 5B](#), the SP-doped LCN “pixel” rows are wired on top of the mini-LED array. Localized priming is achieved by activating mini-LEDs behind only the desired grid spaces. Mini-LEDs were selected because they allowed for focused UV illumination at the pixel level without lithography while still producing sufficient UV intensity output. The checkerboard circuit design, as illustrated in [Figures 5C](#), is selected to enable multiple mini-LEDs to be switched on simultaneously and individually, as recorded in [Video S5](#). Thereby, the letter “I” can be generated by gating material only in the middle column and the bottom and top rows of the array. We utilized this to spell out a word, as depicted and recorded in [Figure 5D](#) and [Video S6](#), respectively. After the UV stimulus is removed, the programmed forms persist in the array until the memory-erasure phenomenon is complete. In this specific device design, this process takes place in less than a second.

Conclusion

We have developed LCNs with the ability to memorize and forget desired actuation behavior through priming and memory-erasing stimuli enabled by the integration of SP dopant to tune its dielectric properties. By applying our material as a dielectric in a capacitor, we translate the molecular effect of the SP-to-MC conversion, via UV illumination, to a macroscopic memorized actuation effect. This action is reversible, and we can trigger the forgetting function by promoting the MC-to-SP back relaxation through light irradiation at a different wavelength, namely green light. We also demonstrate the potential of combining priming and forgetting to dictate smart material behavior for unprecedented applications, such as actuation-based programmable pixel boards. We aim for our LCN memory materials to expand on the functions of responsive materials and act as a foundation for the further development of LCN learning materials based on the principles of classical conditioning. We envision that learning materials, with the ability to adapt to their environment without the need for additional controlling elements, will be ideal to automate functions in systems ranging from advanced medical devices, such as self-acclimating prosthetics, to self-learning materials and synthetic artificial intelligence.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Resource availability

Lead contact

Further information and requests for resources and reagents should be directed to and will be fulfilled by the lead contact, Danqing Liu (d.liu1@tue.nl).

Figure 5. SP-LCN switchable cilia array demonstrator construction and function

(A) 3D illustration of single-pixel capabilities of the SP-LCN cilia demonstrator and the influence of a mini-LED on the gold-coated SP-LCN cilia.

(B) Annotated 3D cross-section of cilia demonstrator displaying (i) control platform for applying electric field to SP-LCN cilia separately, (ii) polylactic acid (PLA) clamps to ensure stable electrical contact across the SP-doped cilia capacitors, (iii) PLA coating to shield the circuitry and SP-LCN material from the environment, (iv) PMMA cover around the mini-LEDs and circuit board, (v) custom printed circuit board (PCB) with mini-LED pixels and end taps for individual control of pixels, (vi) Arduino DUE used to drive the PCB, and (vii) dimensions and design of the gold-coated SP-LCN cilia.

(C) Circuit diagram of the checkerboard design for the pixel-based driving system for the mini-LEDs in the SP-LCN demonstrator.

(D) Highlighted footage of the SP-LCN cilia demonstrator UV gating SP-LCN pixels to display programmable forms, such as the letters "HIM."

Materials availability

This study did not generate new unique reagents.

Data and code availability

All relevant data that support the findings of this work are available from the [lead contact](#) upon reasonable request.

Materials

2-Methyl-1,4-phenylene bis(4-((6-(acryloyloxy)hexyl)oxy)benzoate) (reactive LC monomer RM82) was used as commercially acquired from Henan Daken Chemical. Benzoicure 4-[[6-[(1-oxo-2-propenyl)oxy]hexyl]oxy]-4-methoxyphenylester (reactive LC monomer RM105) was used as commercially acquired from Sigma-Aldrich. Bis(2,4,6-trimethylbenzoyl)-phenylphosphineoxide (photoinitiator agent Irgacure 819) was used as commercially received from Ciba Specialty Chemicals NV. 2,6-Bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-methylphenol (inhibitor agent BHT) was used as acquired commercially from Sigma-Aldrich. Oxolane (solvent THF) was utilized as commercially acquired from Biosolve Chimie SARL. Toluene (solvent) was utilized as commercially acquired from Biosolve Chimie SARL. 1-(2-Hydroxyethyl)-3,3-dimethylindolino-6'-nitrobenzopyrylospiran (SP 1) was used as commercially acquired from TCI. 1,3,3-Trimethylindolino-6'-bromobenzopyrylospiran (SP 2) was used as commercially acquired from TCI. 1,3,3-Trimethylindolino- β -naphthopyrylospiran (SP 3) was

used as commercially acquired from TCI. 1,3,3-Trimethylindolino-8'-methoxybenzopyrrolospiran (SP 4) was used as commercially acquired from TCI. 1,3,3-Trimethylindolino-6'-nitrobenzopyrrolospiran (SP 5) was used as commercially acquired from Sigma-Aldrich. 2-(3',3'-Dimethyl-6-nitrospiro[chromene-2,2'-indol]-1'(3'H)-yl)ethyl methacrylate (SPM) was used as commercially acquired from Flourochem. UVS 91 (UV glue) was acquired from Norland Products and mixed with Micropearls (6 μm silicon spacers) acquired from Sekisui Chemical. Optmer AL 1254 (planar-aligning polyimide) was used as commercially acquired from JSR Micro. Sunever RN-4418(0426) (homeotropic-aligning polyimide) was used as commercially acquired from Nissan Chemical Corporation. Typical SP-doped LCN mixtures used for experiments consist of a 0.24:0.72 M ratio of RM82 and RM105, respectively. 5 wt % SP was added to this typical mixture, accompanied by 2 wt % photoinitiator and 0.25 wt % inhibitor.

SP kinetics and activation quantifications

Experiments were conducted with a variable intensity UV light source (Thorlabs M365L2-C2), between 10.7 and 110.9 Wm^{-2} , with an LED controller (Thorlabs DC4104) within a UV-vis spectrophotometer (PerkinElmer Lambda 750) as illustrated in [Figure S16](#). The intensity of the UV irradiation from the source was measured with a radiometer (RM12 Opsytec Dr. Gröber). The green light absorption associated with MC was tracked to determine material activation with time. The SP was tested in different media including THF, toluene, low-polarity LCs, high-polarity LCs, low-polarity LCNs, and high-polarity LCNs. The optimal SP variant was determined through these tests, as shown in [Figure S17](#), and applied as the SP within all typical SP-doped LCN samples for further testing. The optical properties of full activation of SP within LCNs (5 wt %) was determined by measuring the green light absorbance of MC after illumination of the SP with a maximum UV light intensity of 110 Wm^{-2} until saturation. The UV illumination was retained for 120 min at 110 Wm^{-2} intensity to ensure maximum activation of the SP within the LCN. This absorbance value was used a benchmark to describe the percentage of max absorbance at λ_{max} for experiments with LCN samples with 5 wt % SP doping.

Preparation and alignment of SP-doped LCs

LCs (RM82, RM105) bought from commercial sources were used as is. Planar-alignment-inducing and homeotropic-alignment-inducing polyimides were spin coated (KarlSuss CT62) onto separate sterilized glass slides at 5,000 rpm for 40 s; the glass slide with planar-alignment-inducing polyimide was additionally rubbed in the desired alignment direction to create channels and to ensure effective seeding for planar alignment. The glass slides were then made into a cell using UV glue incorporated with 10 μm silicon spacers. The LC was mixed with a variant of SP, BHT, and Irgacure 819 and melted at 80°C on a hotplate while being stirred at 300 rpm with a magnetic stirrer. SP can be integrated into the LCN in a "free" non-binding form, a monoacrylate side-chain form, or a diacrylate main-chain form. The free form of SP was selected, as it was observed to convert to MC more effectively than the other forms, as shown in [Figure S18](#), allowing for faster and more persistent memory effects where greater deformations and a slower relaxation process are recorded. This is suspected to be due to the bonds that monoacrylate or diacrylate SP makes to the main chains in the LCN hindering the SP-to-MC conversion.⁴¹ The SP-doped LC mixture was then inserted into the pre-heated, polyimide-coated glass cell through capillary forces.

Synthesis of SP-doped LCNs

The SP-doped LC mixture within the pre-prepared glass slide was homogenized at 40°C and illuminated with UV light of intensity 150 Wm^{-2} from an EXFO (OmniCure

Series 2000). The Irgacure 819 was activated within the material to produce free radicals, consuming the BHT dopant and leading to the polymerization of the structure to form LCNs. The prepared glass slide was then cracked open with a razor and placed within distilled water at 50°C. The LCN film was then removed, in an intact manner, from the glass slides. Finally, full polymerization of the LCN was then ensured by post-curing the material at 120°C for 20 min.

Controlling LCN alignment

A polarizing optical microscope (Leica DM6000 M) was used to identify the molecular alignment within the synthesized LCNs. These data were used to confirm the splay alignment within the LCN materials.

Electrical functionalization of SP-doped LCN surfaces to build a capacitor

A sputter coater (Quorum Q 150T S plus) was used to sputter a 10 nm gold layer on both the lower and upper surfaces of an LCN film. The edges of the LCN film were cut off with a razor to ensure there were no gold bridges connecting the upper and lower surfaces. For the miniaturized samples required for the switchable cilia array demonstrator, a mask was used during sputter coating to ensure no gold was sputtered on the edges of the cilia samples. The mask was prepared within specialized CAD software (Vollerun RDWorks v.8.01.18) and then laser cut (CNC Tech XM 3040). Our SP-doped LCN capacitors are expected to last to least 1,500 actuation cycles as long as the electrical field strength within it does not exceed 100 V/ μm .

Testing electrical effects of SP-to-MC conversion within LCNs

The SP-doped LCN films were connected to a potentiostat (BioLogic VMP-300) via electrodes on the separate gold layers on either side of the LCN film. The SP-doped LCN film was modeled as a capacitor and a resistor in series, and galvanostatic electrochemical impedance spectroscopy was performed to collect data on sample impedance with applied frequency. The changes in the impedance of the SP-doped LCN were recorded as the SP-to-MC conversion was triggered by illumination with UV light for 5 min at 110 Wm^{-2} intensity. The UV light lamp and LED controller were used to illuminate the sample.

Electrical setup of electrical actuation experiments and electrical threshold testing

Electrodes were connected on the separate gold layers on either side of the LCN film. AC was supplied by a frequency generator (BK Precision 4054B) and amplified by a voltage amplifier (Falco Systems WMA-300) to allow for voltage and frequency ranges between 0 and 600 V_{pp} and 0 and 30 MHz, respectively. The voltage and frequency threshold parameters were determined through image analysis of SP-doped LCNs stimulated by electric fields with combinations of voltage and frequency at the boundary of the active actuation region. Any additional increase in voltage and frequency parameters of the electric field at the threshold settings would cause an increase in deformation angle. The actuation threshold parameters were considered when deciding the optimal voltage and frequency parameters for actuation tests for our memory phenomenon investigation, where the actuation kinetics were optimized to present the capabilities of our electrical actuator system under the influence of pulsed UV gating as shown in [Figure S19](#). During electrical actuation, contributions from Joule heating and dielectric heating are expected; the individual thermal contributions of these phenomena are not identified, as we focus on the dielectric actuation of the SP-doped LCNs.

Deformation image analysis

Footage and images of electrical actuation were recorded using a high-speed camera (Olympus OM-D E-M10 Mark IV). Footage recorded by the camera was processed into frames on MATLAB. Image analysis was performed to quantify deformation in terms of bending angle using functions within specialized software (Fiji/ImageJ 2.9.0). The splay alignment of the SP-doped LCN films and the experimental setup were selected to facilitate this procedure; specifically, the experimental setup uses two electrodes on clamp tips, each of which individually make contact with one of the two separate surfaces of the gold-coated, SP-doped LCN film, connecting it to the circuit as a capacitor. This also allows the splay-aligned SP-doped LCN films are able to bend freely once sufficient electrical stimulus is applied. The bending deforming is clearly visible and can easily be quantified through image analysis as a deformation angle, which is based on the position of the free end of the SP-doped LCN film. The free end of the SP-doped LCN film was selected as the reference point for deformation because this area of the film cannot deform and is also displaced the most during actuation, making it simple and reliable to track. This also makes this method especially useful when comparing separate films. Despite there being no significant effect on actuation behavior, light exposure in experiments was always directed onto the planarly aligned surface of the LCNs.

Sample temperature tracking and dielectric and gating mechanism investigation

The temperature of our LCNs during experimentation was tracked using an IR camera (Fluke Ti32), a high-speed IR camera (Xenics Gobi), and a contact thermometer (Kane-May KM340). This was used to confirm the dielectric and dielectric-heating actuation mechanisms for SP-doped LCN actuators as a dielectric material within a capacitor, as well as to investigate the heating effect of UV illumination.

Switchable array demonstrator setup

The array demonstrator was designed in CAD software (Dassault Systemes Solidworks 2021–2022) and described electronically in the PCB CAD software (KiCAD 7.0). The resulting schematics were produced by manufacturer PCBway. The control chip (Arduino DUE Board) of the demonstrator was programmed (Arduino IDE 2.1.0) to allow for switching the power supplied to the UV mini-LEDs (Vishay VLMU1610-365-135) and the modes at which power is supplied. End taps (Omron D2FS-FL-N) were integrated into the circuitry to allow for switching between modes without needing to reupload Arduino code to the Arduino DUO. UV mini-LEDs were used to supply the UV stimulus and were soldered into place with soldering paste (Conrad BLF03) under the SP-doped LCN cilia. General soldering of the circuitry was performed with a soldering station (Multicomp Pro MP740029). 47 Ω through-hole resistors (Thomsen 423203) were used to protect the mini-LEDs from overloading. The SP-doped LCN array was driven by the frequency generator and voltage amplifier. Electric fields with optimized voltage and frequency parameters were tailored for each channel of the SP-doped LCN in the demonstrator to ensure equal stimulation; slight variations in actuation thresholds of the gold-coated, SP-doped LCN strips were present due to human error during material processing. Each SP-doped LCN pixel in the array was illuminated with approximately 110 Wm^{-2} UV intensity upon activation of the underlying UV mini-LED. This value is the true intensity within the SP-doped LCN pixel after the absorption factor of the 10 nm gold layers sputtered on the sample has been considered. The casing for the demonstrator was produced by 3D printing (Ultimaker S5) a poly(lactic acid) filament. Poly(methyl methacrylate) was used as a spacer between the SP-doped LCN cilia and the mini-LEDs to avoid obstruction to the actuation of the LCN.

SUPPLEMENTAL INFORMATION

Supplemental information can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matt.2024.03.001>.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Conceptualization, D.L.; methodology, D.L. and M.O.A.; software, S.W.; validation, M.O.A.; formal analysis, M.O.A. and T.-H.L.; investigation, M.O.A., T.-H.L., and A.v.B.; resources, D.L.; data curation, M.O.A.; writing – original draft, M.O.A.; writing – review & editing, M.O.A. and D.L.; visualization, M.O.A. and D.L.; supervision, D.L.; project administration, D.L. and M.O.A.; funding acquisition, D.L.

DECLARATION OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no competing interests.

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